

TYPES OF DISCUSSION REGARDING SPECIALIZATION IN MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS

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ANNOTATION: In this article, there are decisions and opinions about the work carried out in the native language textbooks regarding the types of debates for specialization, and there are views on the subject being understood. In relation to the use of phrases and sentences used in the teaching of the mother tongue, it is effective to practically use the types of arguments related to specialization in the teaching of the mother tongue, in relation to the significance of modern educational technologies, in contrast to the traditional teaching methods of certain topics and skills. brings about. Also, the use of debates in improving the effectiveness of the lesson leads to better efficiency.

KEY WORDS: Discussion, debate, art of rhetoric, art of discussion, listener, speaker, observation technology.

It is considered appropriate for the teacher to artificially organize problematic situations in mother tongue classes. It is also observed that pre-exam familiarization classes or in the company of students who are generally unknown to the teacher are explained by giving problem situations as the main tool of the teacher. the orator must restrain himself, respect the interlocutor and his opinion." "Today there are several types of the art of arguing. Discussion is the coming to a certain conclusion of opinions and opinions on a certain issue. In the discussion, all aspects of the subject of the debate will be looked at. Each of the participants of the topic expresses his free opinion. Eristics is the art of arguing. Originally, in ancient Greece, the art of finding the truth with the help of dispute was widespread as a means of persuading people.

Eristics was developed by the sophists and appeared as an art of discussion, debate and polemic. Debate means a dispute between the parties on an issue. During the debate, each participant tries to prove that he is right. In the discussion [1] Also, the purpose of practical organization of debates and discussions about expertise, which is widely used in mother tongue classes, is to demonstrate the ability to reason and, moreover, to express the thoughts and opinions of the student-young people. the art form counts. It can be said that the expressive implementation of practical views on the artificial organization of the discussion process of the types of debates related to specialization creates uniqueness. Accordingly, there are certain peculiarities in the teacher's artificial implementation of the debate on expertise. They are as follows:

- Being able to think freely;
- acquaintance with peers;
- formation of speech;
- getting new information;
- generalization of ideas;

- have special knowledge;
- listening skills;
- possibility to save time;
- study of manipulation;
- learning the art of management

and it is explained by the fact that the importance of such things is great in our daily life. Also, it can be said that the creation of artificial debates for entering the specialty or for the generalized expression of opinions and considerations related to the specialty provides its effectiveness as well as the level of significance. "What is the debate? According to the encyclopedic dictionary, a discussion (lat. discussio - discussion, research) is "a debate aimed at reaching the truth using only the right methods of persuasion." The discussion is aimed at reaching some truth, and this or that truth becomes a "common victory" for both sides. There are no clear winners in the debate. In the course of the discussion, previously incomprehensible points are explained more deeply and clearly. And even if the parties "do not come to an agreement, they ... come to a mutual understanding in conversation." The ability to properly discuss is in demand and relevant in the modern world. By teaching students to discuss, in particular, subjects such as international law, international relations and world economy, we help future specialists in these areas to stand on their feet and effectively communicate with colleagues in the workplace in their professional activities, conduct dialogues, negotiations, to act constructively in conflict situations and others".[2]

In addition, it can be explained by the fact that the use of other forms of debate in increasing the mutual importance of organizing debates about expertise has preserved the level of expediency. Debate. Debate is considered a means of exchange of ideas and opinions between people, and in the case where people are divided into two sides as a result of mutual views, it is considered an exchange of opinions. Bah the formal appearance of s is called debate, and there are views that debate, discussion, and argument are carried out on the basis of the combined force under a common meaning.

Judging from the above thoughts and opinions, the organization of debates on entering the specialty in the mother tongue classes will also help to increase the level of knowledge of the student-young people in the field of specialization they have chosen. Accordingly, it can be said that most of the arguments used in native language textbooks are carried out in the form of information. It should be mentioned that the performance of specially defined procedures is required in the conduct of debate games. In this:

1. Approver 1;
2. Affirmative 2;
3. Conclusion 3

is observed to be carried out in the following manner. The educational purpose of games such as discussions and debates requires students to think freely, to be able to use their mental abilities in a free environment, as well as to implement them in connection with certain information about the specialties they want to acquire.

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